

Oral (S15-419, Time: Thursday 15:10, Room: Bodensee)

Influence of injection moulding process parameters on industrial Polyhydroxyalkanoates properties for medical device applications

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This work was initiated with the motivation of using bio-based polymers in high-end medical applications to achieve circularity and to reduce environmental impact. In this work, injection and micro injection moulding of bio-based polymers are studied with industrial grade of Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs). PHAs can be processed with injection moulding but some material properties and processing conditions provide bottlenecks for high-end applications such as in medical devices. The aim of this research is to systematically reveal the bottlenecks for the implementation of such materials in high volume and highly demanding industrial applications. Initial thermal characterization of the materials was done using Differential Scanning Calorimetry and Dynamic Mechanical and Thermal Analysis to understand the behaviour of PHAs in a molten condition. Five moulding process parameters – Injection speed, Injection temperature, Injection pressure, Packing pressure, and Mould temperature - were identified as critical parameters to produce test parts. The moulded samples were subjected to physical and mechanical testing to reveal the the effect of the material degradation on their properties. Attention was paid to the evolution of the properties with the post-moulding crystallization of the bio-polyesters. The results of these analyses are presented along with the reflection on the identified limitations for industrial applications of PHAs in medical devices.